

Simulating and Visualizing Persons Movement in Deck Arrangements: an Web-Based Approach

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Abstract. This paper introduces a novel, open-source web-based simulation program that models and visualize in real time person movement scenarios with deck arrangement (GA) as user input. Ship evacuation analysis is critical to maritime safety, directly influencing ship design and emergency preparedness across various vessel types. International maritime regulations, such as the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS), mandate stringent safety requirements for ships. For specialized vessels like Service Operation Vessels (SOVs) that support offshore industries, the Code of Safety for Special Purpose Ships (SPS Code) and the Code for the Carriage of Industrial Personnel (IP Code) provide additional guidelines to ensure the safety of industrial personnel on board. Academic research underscores the need for precise evacuation modeling to bolster safety protocols and ship design. However, current evacuation simulation tools are often hampered by significant drawbacks. These include high costs, proprietary constraints, and a lack of adaptability to the unique configurations of different ship types, such as SOVs and other vessels carrying industrial personnel. In many instances, these tools are overly complex and relatively slow, particularly in the initial stages of the Ship Design process. We are currently developing the tool using JavaScript libraries for 3D visualization, aiming to provide an interactive real-time platform for users to observe personal movement processes. We focus on creating a flexible and customizable tool that can adapt to different ship layouts, particularly for SOVs and ships governed by the SPS and IP codes. This adaptability ensures that the tool can cater to your specific needs in ship design and safety protocols. We present case studies that illustrate the potential of the tool in ship layout evaluation. These studies demonstrate how the tool can be used to identify bottlenecks and enhance design layouts. The open-source nature of the program fosters collaboration within the maritime community, encouraging continuous improvement and future adoption.

Key words: *Evacuation, general arrangement, design*

1. The Importance of Studying and Simulating Ship Evacuation

In the last decade or so, the number of passengers, crew and now also industrial personnel has been increasing significantly. Passenger ships have several thousand passengers, offshore vessels can have more than several hundred specialized personnel. This concentration of people on board makes it difficult to evacuate, muster or move between different types of compartments on the ship. Passenger evacuation in current regulations is mainly addressed in SOLAS Convention[1], the FSS Code[2] and IMO MSC/Circ. 1533[3]. SOLAS and the FSS Code contain simple rules describing requirements for width, corridors, staircases or doors. IMO document MSC/Circ. 1533[3] introduced a mandatory evacuation analysis for passenger ships built after 1 January 2020. This document presents the possibility of using a simplified as well as an advanced evacuation simulation method. However, it can be assumed that for ships with particularly complex spatial subdivisions, the method based on advanced assumptions will be more convenient[4].

The modelling of the onboarding process is based on several methods. Some of the most popular include[5], [6], [7]: regression models, queuing models, path choice model, gas-kinetic and cellular automaton model[8], [9], [10]. Some of these models have been implemented in software used to simulate

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the evacuation process on board a ship. Among the most popular of these we can include: EVI[11],[12], MaritimeEXODUS[13], VELOS[14], [15], AENEAS[16]. Table 1. provides information on the methods used in selected programs to simulate the evacuation process.

Software	Methods
EVI	Agent Based with hybrid grid-based+Social forces
MaritimeEXODUS	Agent Based with grid
VELOS	Agent Based
AENEAS	Cellular Automation

Table 1. Evacuation software used in the maritime industry

The issue of the dynamics of on-board movement with reference to evacuation is now widely researched. Arshad[5] identified 115 items of literature on the subject. Most of these publications are related to the evacuation process itself, but there are few references[6], [17], [18] to the design of the vessel, especially in their preliminary stages. Figure 1. depicts a ship evacuation process sequence considering key factors: environmental, configuration, behavioral and human ([5])

Figure 1. Visualization of the evacuation process highlighting evacuation factors ([5])

It therefore seems to us that further work on the implementation of human dynamics on board is an important topic for scientific work. At the same time, the availability of commercial software only makes research in this area difficult. Often these applications have a closed architecture and do not allow easy and fairly automatic interfacing with other tools used in the design process. Therefore, our aim in this article is to propose an open-source software that can be adapted and developed over the years for better modeling of the movement of people, but also for linking it to other programs. In our case, the configuration (GA), behavioral (path rule) and human factors (speed, mobility) will be considered. As far the authors known, there is no real open source / software toolbox available for real-time assessment of persons movement analysis.

2. Web-Based Maritime Simulations: Apps and Objects

2.1. Maritime Web Apps

The possibilities of Webapps are gaining momentum in the last years, with works advocating the use of software development practices and JavaScript as a serious tool in engineering, as exemplified by the Ship

Design and Operations Lab group at NTNU [19][20]. Most of the examples of that the group have been working with are available online, converging towards a library of examples that can be accessed, edited and copied, exemplified by the Vessel.JS, <https://vesseljs.org/>, [4]. Figure 2. shows a part of this library. Each of the examples is a piece that follows similar structure as described previous, regarding versioning, re-use of code and online repositories. Similar compilation of codes and web-application is also practice in other research groups.

Figure 2. Vessel.JS Library Portfolio

The general arrangement (GA) of a ship is probably the most important unique document resulting from the Concept Phase and in subsequently maintaining the coherence of that design. Many ship designers consider the development of a new and functional GA as almost an art, where an experienced designer lays the fundamental arrangements, for ever greater detail to be inserted later in the ship design process [22]. Specifically for the modeling and visualtion of GA, since 2016 an online a simplified 2D design tool inspired by Andrew’s Design Building Block (DBB) has been available as a joint collaboration between UCL and NTNU. The first version of the tool was developed at UCL and can be accessed at <http://dbb.ucl.im/2016> [23]. An extended version was developed by Kramel[24] in 2019 at NTNU, including a more comprehensive resistance analyses as well as closed-form functions for seakeeping (vertical movement, acceleration and roll), observed at <http://dbb.ucl.im>. Figure 3. presents the dashboard of the 2015 tool, which receives GA as 2D elements, and was used as basis for the development of our tool with GA as 3D objects. The app reads the GA from a database (.csv file), plot the blocks into a grid and evaluate their positioning, attributes, neighbours and connections.

2.2. GA and Persons as Computational Objects

In the context of an evacuation process, the primary computational objects to be considered in the context of a ship are its GA, decomposed as: *Deck*, *Spaces*, *Compartments* and *Interfaces* con configurational factors, plus *Person* considering behavioral and human factors.

Deck is the main object. This object contains basic information about the GA itself but also contains methods that can be associated with interaction with the external environment. In the evacuation process itself, the facility is a full legal element of the simulation. It usually acts as a container for the other object types.

Let us start the description of the main objects present in the simulation process with *spaces*. A deck is an object that contains the individual rooms of a ship and the corridors, or objects that connect these rooms. A corridor is a special type of object that can be described as spatially free from the Compartments on board. By defining an object in this way, it does not need to have a geometrical description, that is, a *space*.

Compartments are objects that have their own geometry. Other compartment properties include the type of compartment as well as the filling. Loading-related information can include the type of cargo and its properties, such as COG and free surface for liquid cargo. The last type of object related to the evacuation

Figure 3. Ship Design Layout Tool - web-based tool for modelling and analyses of GAs[21]

process is Interfaces[22]. Interfaces describe the connections between Compartments and Spaces. The evacuation process itself can only take place in Compartments and Spaces. However, a full simulation must operate with all 3 types of facilities.

Doors and Stairs are considered *interfaces*. The attributes of Interfaces are, among others, position, width, height and also, the Compartments or Spaces it connects. This object plays a key role in more complex evacuation cases. Main evacuation points such as the Mustering Station are also modeled as Interfaces. Interfaces are the objects that Persons are trying to reach.

The four object types described above are the objects required in the evacuation simulation process. In a world *where everything is an object*, a Person can also be described as an object with its properties and methods.

The basic attributes of a *Person* object include its location, age and gender. Age and gender are required[3] to determine walking speed in Compartments, Areas and Interfaces. The algorithm for moving people on board a ship considering the above three object types can be divided into two parts: global pathfinding towards the nearest interface and obstacle avoidance.

The main idea is the approach, with the Person seeing the place they are going to. In a Compartment, this assumption is entirely correct, especially about the Interface between this Compartment and another Compartment. However, this assumption has more weaknesses when talking about a destination point from a global point of view, such as Mustering Station. At this stage of model development, however, it can be assumed that Persons know exactly where the Target Point is. This assumption allows the Person to move by the shortest route towards the Target Point without any obstacle in the environment. A motion vector, a mathematical representation of a person's movement direction and speed in 2 dimensions, is determined based on each Person's speed and the distance to the Target Point. The motion vector is decomposed into movement in the X and Y directions. This algorithm is repeated until each Person reaches the Target Point. If any simulated People encounter an obstacle, a different algorithm is used, as described in the following paragraph.

When such a potential collision or boundary violation is detected, the algorithm initiates an obstacle avoidance mode. In this mode, the algorithm randomly selects an initial avoidance direction, either upward or downward, to try to circumvent the obstacle. The Person then executes incremental vertical movements in the chosen direction to navigate around the obstacle. However, the chosen vertical path also collides or leads the Person outside the deck limits. In that case, the Person is temporarily stuck, and their unsuccessful attempt count is incremented. After a predefined number of unsuccessful attempts (in this case, three), the algorithm reverses the vertical avoidance direction, enabling the exploration of alternative routes to bypass the obstacle.

Interactions between Persons are based on a simplified model of Social Forces with minor modifications to make the modeling easier. Approaching Persons slow down to avoid interactions, but when a collision cannot be avoided, a random choice is made for each Person to wait one turn or to change direction.

3. Persons Movement Tool: Workflow, Pseudocode and Dashboard

3.1. Evacuation simulation workflow

The evacuation simulation workflow can be explained as any other input, calculation/simulation and output system, Figure 4.

Figure 4. Evacuation simulation workflow

The GUI centralises all input and output that the user can manage. It provides interactivity and immediate response. Within the GUI, the output part can also be distinguished. The input part is related to uploading the general plan and setting the number of people participating in the simulation.

- Input 1.1 - Loading a JSON file from which a 3D General Arrangement Plan is created
- Input 1.2 - Interaction with the 3d model of the General Arrangement Plan, possibility to move Rooms and rotate the view itself
- Input 1.3 - Visual representation of the deck layout with Compartments, Interfaces and Mustering Station.

- Input 1.4 - Random distribution of persons on the deck
- Input 1.5 - Main rules of Person movement on the Deck with or without Interfaces
- Input 1.6 - Main rules of collision avoidance with Compartments
- Simulation 2.1 - Functions related to the Interface and its achievement.
- Simulation 2.2 - The main method associated with determining the route to the Interfaces and Mustering station using the rules defined in Input 1.5.
- Simulation 2.3 - The main method associated with collision avoidance with Compartments using the rules defined in Input 1.6.
- Simulation 2.4 - Functions related to the Target Point and its achievement.
- Output 3.1 - 3D layout of the deck based on a combination of the model from a JSON file and manually modifying the position of individual Objects
- Output 3.2 - Results related to the completion of the evacuation simulation. Graphical and textual representation of the route taken by a person from the starting point to the Mustering Station.

Walking rules as mentioned in the previous chapter are based on a simplified version of the Social Force model.

3.2. Pseudo Code

Once the application is open and online, the algorithm can be accessed and modified. The pseudo code describes the main function as follows.

```
function loadGeometryFile()
    CREATE deckArrangement based of JSON file

function createCompartments()
    CREATE 3D mesh of compartments
    CREATE Bounding Box of compartments

function AddMusteringStation()
    CREATE 3D mesh of mustering station
    CREATE Bounding Box of mustering station

function createInterfaces()
    CREATE 3D mesh of interface

class Human
    Class represent a person taking part in a simulation of on-deck movement
    constructor(id, speed, color) - Constructor Human class instance

function createPerson(num)
    DRAW the location of a Person on board
    CREATE 3D mesh of Person

function interfaceAwareMovement(person)
    CHECK if Person is in the room
    SET Interfaces as a target point for a person to leave the Compartment

function directMovement(person)
```

CHECK person collision with compartments
WALK person shorts route to Interface or Mustering Station

The system is built around seven core functions: *loadGeometryFile*, *createCompartments*, *AddMusteringStation*, *createInterfaces*, *createPerson*, *interfaceAwareMovement* and *directMovement*. These functions are implemented within the JavaScript code and serve as the foundation for the application's logic. Each of them performs a specific role in setting up and managing the simulation environment.

An additional *animate* function is used to perform all operations related to the real-time display of the simulation results.

3.3. GUI and Dashboard

The tool was developed online, a web-app. This was paramount due to the advantages in terms of sharing, compatibility, open source development and creation of graphic user interfaces, or GUIs [19][25]. Compared to traditional engineering programming environments, web technologies provide more options and freedom for the creation of sophisticated user interfaces. The developer of a web application may use sliders, text fields and buttons to gather inputs from the user. Results can be presented as formatted text, tables, plots or interactive visualisations, either 2D or 3D. Multiple textual and graphic elements can be combined in dashboards to present a cohesive experience to the user, allowing them to vary inputs and observe the effects of the variation on the results in real-time.

Figure 5. Dashboard for the Web-based tool (<https://wtif.pl/evacuation/>)

The fact that it is possible to share web simulations with anyone who has access to an internet connection makes the approach convenient to give distributed users access to the same model. This centralization also allows unified support of the application, as once the developer deploys a new version of the source code online, all users instantly obtain access to it. Such applications are compatible with any modern device with a web browser. While at this point most consumers take it for granted that a web service is going to work seamlessly on their devices, this advantage, in the context of engineering simulations, overcomes common compatibility issues related to operational system type or version, dependence on frameworks or on installation of programming languages. From the point of view of scientific research, the openness assures that other researchers can verify and validate the algorithm and its results. From the point of view of development, it facilitates the creation of new features by providing access to libraries and frameworks

for diverse purposes. Conversely, by publishing a new idea as an open web app, one allows others to reuse any element of the tool (e.g. grid, plots, algorithms).

Figure 5. presents an overview of the dashboard, found at <https://wtif.pl/evacuation/>. The behavioral and human code of every person can be altered via the script within the code, while a new GA can be uploaded as an object from a JSON file. The application offers three layout options. Two of these are built-in; one of these is IMO-compliant [3]. The third option enables users to upload any GA from a JSON file. The number of Persons participating in the simulation must be selected once the appropriate GA has been set. The next step is to run the simulation and observe the movement of the persons on board. Once the simulation has been completed, the results can be viewed on a graph. It is also possible to download the results for each person involved in the simulation. The user may download these files for further analysis.

4. Case study - 80 persons movement Simulation

Figure 6. provides a screenshot of the simulation's initial state, designed to test evacuation efficiency towards the designated red mustering station. This scenario involves 80 simulated individuals (green 'Persons'), who are initially distributed evenly across the main sections of the blue deck area. The yellow compartments are arranged to mimic a proposed new operational layout. The figure displays this core simulation environment directly, without any user interface elements, allowing for an unobstructed view of the starting conditions.

Figure 6. Simulation environment without Interface all Person only on deck (yellow compartments, red mustering station, blue deck, green Person)

Following this setup, Figure 7. illustrates the dynamic results of the simulation, specifically charting the routes and complex movement patterns of these 80 Persons as they navigate towards the mustering station. The traces clearly show convergence towards main thoroughfares, but also highlight areas of potential congestion around narrowly spaced compartments. By examining these paths, which evolved from the initial conditions in Figure 6., we can begin to assess the practicality of the proposed layout and identify potential bottlenecks that might impede rapid movement. Raw results from each person, such as coordinates at each timestep (and consequently speed and acceleration) can be accessed as output in the dashboard (SAVE RESULTS) button.

5. Concluding Remarks and Future Work

The web-based approach is already a viable solution for the development of several maritime engineering simulations and presents advantages in terms of speed, compatibility, development tools and user interface [25]. Such advantages are: Platform-independent, as it can be used without prior set-up or installation, working on modern computers, tablet or mobile; Extensive use of available open libraries, e.g., for solution of mathematical models, creation of 2D plots and rendering of 3D scenes; Interactive GUIs, allowing the simulations to convey meaning easily to users, including those who do not have an engineering background

The open tool here discussed is a working in process, and much of the libraries and methods intends to be improved in the years to come. The web-based accessibility and open nature of this model encourage broader testing and feedback from a diverse user base with varied experiences. Its interactive feature,

Figure 7. Simulation results for initial situation from Figure 6.

allowing users to reposition compartments on the deck, facilitates a preliminary analysis of how such modifications impact personnel movement.

The use of open web technology, even in this initial, imperfect iteration, allows for early-stage design integration. This means the tool can be relatively easily incorporated with other design process components, such as optimizing compartment layouts on decks.

Currently, the tool serves more as a proof-of-concept tool for checking the quality of ship layout rather than as typical software for simulating the evacuation process. The tool is intended to demonstrate first and foremost that it is possible to use open source software and show the feasibility of applying a single source of truth, such as the object-oriented model of a ship, in the design process. Since the primary purpose of this research was to show that it is possible to create open-source software that can be used in research and in simple preliminary ship design, it is impossible to identify the validity of any available software. In the past, there was software used to simulate evacuation called FDS-Evac[26][27], but it is currently no longer being developed. At the same time, FDS-Evac software was not available via a Web interface.

Future work will focus on the case of simulating more complex configurations and human behavior, as well as multiple deck movement. Currently, the movement model has limitations. The assumption that individuals follow the absolute shortest route to a target point is suboptimal, as evidenced by simulation results. Often, a more direct path to the target point, initiated earlier with proactive avoidance of compartments, would be more efficient. Another crucial future development will be the introduction of interactions between individuals. This could be achieved using a pheromone model, similar to that described by Gökce *et al*[28]. At present, individuals only alter their course upon collision with a compartment or another person. The next iteration of the onboard movement model should implement a full Social Force model[29] to enable more natural obstacle avoidance. At this stage of development, the model has not yet been fully tested according to the IMO MSC.1/Circ.1533[3] Guidelines. After expanding the model of the alternation of Individuals and the interaction between them, it is planned to show compliance with the IMO document[3].

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